

Interference :

In the determination of 5 ppm of manganese at pH 9.1 ± 0.1 the following ions do not interfere to the extents ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) given in the parentheses: CH_3COO^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , or $\text{B}_4\text{O}_7^{2-}$ (500); PO_4^{3-} (100); Na^+ , K^+ , Li^+ , Rb^+ or Cs^+ (500); Ba^{2+} or Sr^{2+} (250); Ag^+ (50); Cd^{2+} (20); MoO_4^{2-} or WO_4^{2-} (20). However, Cu^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , VO_3^- , EDTA and fluoride seriously interfere at all concentrations. The use of common masking agents to eliminate their interferences was not fruitful.

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Simultaneous Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium and Uranium with 4-Methyl Daphnetin

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VANADIUM and uranium metals are frequently mined together. Although reliable analytical procedures for their determination are known, very little work has appeared on the simultaneous spectrophotometric analysis of these metals.

4-methyl daphnetin forms an orange-yellow complex with uranium (λ_{max} 450 nm) and a bluish-green complex with vanadium (λ_{max} 600 nm) in the pH range 5 and 7. The present work reports a simple and quick simultaneous spectrophotometric method of analysis of vanadium and uranium with 4-methyl daphnetin.

From the spectrophotometric properties of the complexes.

Complex	λ_{max} nm	ϵ_{450}	ϵ_{600}	Sandell sensitivity $\mu\text{g/cm}^2$
V(v)-4-methyl daphnetin	600	6375	900	0.006
U(vi)-4-methyl daphnetin	450	2700	0	0.030

The relationships (1) and (2)

$$A_{450} = \epsilon_{450}^V [V] + \epsilon_{450}^U [U] \quad (1)$$

$$A_{600} = \epsilon_{600}^V [V] + \epsilon_{600}^U [U] \quad (2)$$

were used to develop the following equations :

$$[V] \times 10^4 = 1.266 A_{600}$$

$$[U] \times 10^4 = 3.7 A_{450} - 3.4 A_{600}$$

Several synthetic mixtures were prepared and analysed satisfactorily.

Procedure

To an aliquot containing 0.8 to 1.6 μg of V (v) and 10-25 μg of UO_2^{2+} is added 4 ml of 0.1M alcoholic solution of 4-methyl daphnetin. The pH of the solution is adjusted between 5 and 7 and the resulting solution diluted to 25 ml. The absorbance of the solutions are measured at 450 and 600 nm against the corresponding reagent blank. The amounts of metals are computed from the appropriate simultaneous equations. A large number of anions do not interfere in the estimation, however Mo, Fe, Ti, W interfere and should be eliminated.

Structures of the Reaction Products from Reaction of Resorcinol with N-Benzoyl Phthalimide

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AN organic dye has been synthesised by the condensation of Resorcinol with N-Benzoyl phthalimide which is a known compound. It behaves like florescene, a dye.